

Teachers' Attitude Towards Multiculturalism and Diversity of Learners in Relation to Students' Academic Performance of Araling Panlipunan

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Nerelia L. Alpon

Master Teacher 1, Domingo Lacson National High School
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9411-543X>

Abstract:

This study examines the relationship between teachers' attitudes toward multiculturalism and learner diversity in relation to the academic performance of Grade 10 students in Araling Panlipunan within the Division of Bacolod City. Using a descriptive research design, the study analyzed various factors, including teachers' demographics, attitudes, and perceptions of multiculturalism and diversity. Findings indicate that teachers generally exhibit a moderately positive attitude toward multiculturalism and a high extent of recognition of learner diversity. However, while no significant relationship was found between teachers' attitudes toward multiculturalism and student academic performance, a significant relationship was established between teachers' recognition of learner diversity and students' academic achievement. Based on these results, a development program was proposed to enhance teachers' awareness of multiculturalism and equip them with strategies to address learner diversity effectively. The study underscores the importance of culturally responsive teaching in fostering an inclusive and equitable educational environment.

Keywords: Academic Performance, multiculturalism and diversity, teachers' attitude

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Teachers play a crucial role in shaping students' academic performance and behavior, particularly in multicultural settings. Their attitudes toward diversity influence how effectively they engage with students from different backgrounds. As stated in the 1987 Constitution, schools must promote patriotism, ethical values, human rights, and critical thinking, which require teachers to embrace multicultural education. Understanding learner diversity involves recognizing differences in race, sex, religion, and socio-economic status, allowing teachers to tailor their approaches for effective learning. Teachers serve as managers, facilitators, and evaluators of student performance, making cultural competence essential in fostering an inclusive environment. To achieve this, educators must be aware of their biases, respect diverse cultures, and apply inclusive teaching strategies that support every student's learning needs (Cagle, 2010).

The National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) emphasize recognizing student individuality and designing diverse learning activities that align with their needs. Multicultural attitudes vary among teachers, impacting students' learning styles, multiple intelligences, and overall academic success. A culturally responsive education fosters fairness and equality by incorporating varied teaching methods, flexible grouping, and collaboration to create an inclusive learning environment (Ortiz, 2012). Teachers' multicultural attitudes directly affect students' academic performance, particularly in subjects like Araling Panlipunan 10, where cultural awareness and historical context are crucial. Examining the impact of teachers' perspectives on diversity can help improve teaching strategies, ensuring that students receive the necessary support to achieve academic success.

In line with this issue, the researcher had been personally motivated to find out the teachers' multicultural attitude, the diversity of learners and the factors affecting student's academic performance in Araling Panlipunan 10 in the Division of Bacolod City as basis for teachers' development program

Current State of Knowledge

Classrooms today are increasingly multicultural, requiring educators to stay informed on current methodologies in multicultural education. Creating an inclusive learning environment benefits diverse students, fostering academic success and mutual understanding between teachers and learners (McIntyre, 2012). A multicultural classroom embraces language differences, celebrates diversity, and promotes tolerance, viewing differences as strengths rather than limitations. Case studies, such as Malaysia's Vision Schools, demonstrate how shared learning spaces can enhance cultural awareness and cooperation, highlighting the need for teachers to possess a multicultural mindset, pedagogical proficiency, and a well-structured curriculum (Malakolunthun et al., 2010). Additionally, studies on teacher candidates emphasize the importance of developing cultural sensitivity through curriculum improvements that integrate multicultural issues. Constructivist theories, particularly social learning and cognitive dissonance,

suggest that behaviors and attitudes are shaped through social interactions, reinforcing the need for inclusive teaching approaches (Vygotsky, 1986; Bandura, 1986). However, many higher education institutions lack effective diversity-focused coursework, underscoring the need for leadership initiatives to enhance pedagogical understanding and practical multicultural competence (Alenan et al., 2010).

Multicultural attitudes are shaped by knowledge, beliefs, emotions, and behaviors, influencing how teachers interact with diverse learners (Adams & Banks, 2010). Jeremy Harmer (2015) highlights four key teacher responsibilities: creating the need for learning, providing formative feedback, fostering a supportive atmosphere, and effectively passing on knowledge. As classrooms grow increasingly diverse, educators must navigate challenges posed by English language learners, students with disabilities, gifted learners, and those from various cultural backgrounds. Nearly 42% of U.S. public school students are minorities, 20% speak a language other than English at home, and 14% have identified disabilities, making teaching both complex and enriching. The push for standards-based reform aims to ensure all students, especially historically underperforming groups, meet uniform academic goals (Volts et al., 2016). However, while student diversity rises, the teaching force remains predominantly homogenous, with only 13.5% of teachers being minorities compared to 31.5% of students. Addressing this gap requires stronger recruitment and support initiatives for minority educators to create a more inclusive and representative educational system. Differentiated instruction allows students to reflect, assess their understanding, and engage creatively while meeting academic standards (McCarthy, 2015). Educational policies emphasize that reducing skill disparities enhances overall academic achievement without compromising quality. To be effective in the 21st century, teachers must develop communication, literacy, and career-readiness skills while adapting to technological advancements and diverse classrooms (Bilbao et al., 2015). Inclusive teaching strategies, cooperative learning, and culturally responsive curricula ensure equal opportunities for all students, including those with special needs. Technology enhances learning by simulating real-world problems through multimedia tools, fostering student engagement. Additionally, teacher exchange programs like Global Teacher Exchange, VIF, and Fulbright Exchange provide opportunities for professional growth, leadership development, and cultural immersion, helping educators embrace diversity and improve their teaching effectiveness.

Culturally responsive education extends beyond classroom practices to encompass administrative policies, procedures, and curricula that address the diverse needs of students, considering cultural, linguistic, and socioeconomic factors. Understanding students' values enables educators to create learning opportunities that align with both academic goals and intrinsic motivations (Hoosien, 2014). Research highlights that teachers' awareness and sensitivity to multiculturalism enhance instructional strategies, assessments, and overall learning environments. Teachers with a deep understanding of students' ethnic and cultural backgrounds foster positive, inclusive, and interactive classrooms, where all voices are valued (Vasquez-Montilla et al., 2014). Additionally, studies reveal that teachers' attitudes towards multicultural education vary based on demographic factors such as nationality, gender, and experience abroad (Gursoy, 2016). Educators who have taught in foreign countries generally demonstrate a stronger commitment to multicultural education, emphasizing the importance of student exchange programs and international teaching experiences in teacher training. Further, prospective teachers' attitudes towards multicultural education are influenced by their conceptions of teaching and learning, highlighting the need for comprehensive training in culturally responsive pedagogy (Koc & Koybasi, 2016).

Studies highlight the strong connection between teachers' pedagogical beliefs, competence, and students' academic performance. Perdigueros (2015) found that teachers with positive pedagogical beliefs demonstrated commitment, leading to high performance ratings and improved student learning. Tingson (2015) revealed that experienced teachers at Victorias National High School showed competence based on NCBS-TSNA Domains, with students' academic performance approaching proficiency. Luna (2015) assessed multicultural education at Far Eastern University, finding discrepancies between teachers' and students' perceptions, indicating a need for program enhancements. Nuqui et al. (2015) determined that while student performance was generally good, no significant relationship existed between pupil, teacher, and school-related factors. Andaya (2016) found that instructional factors significantly influenced the academic performance of Indigenous People (IP) students, while individual and classroom management factors had minimal impact. Joernaldo (2016) noted that in implementing the Grade 8-12 curriculum, learning experiences and resources were often overlooked, affecting students' performance. Lastly, Garcia (2016) found that teachers' high personal attributes, such as intelligence, emotional stability, and creativity, contributed positively to their teaching performance, emphasizing the role of personal and professional qualities in educational success.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study was anchored on Biological System Theory by Urie Bronfenbrenner (2015). The theory was the basis and framework for the conduct of this study. According to Bronfenbrenner (2015) it looks at a child's development within the context of the system of relationships that form his or her environment. Bronfenbrenner's theory defines complex "layers" of environment, each having an effect on a child's development. This theory has recently been renamed "bioecological systems theory" to emphasize that a child's own biology is a primary environment fueling her development. The interaction between factors in the child's maturing biology, his immediate family/community

environment, and the societal landscape fuels and steers his development. Changes or conflict in any one layer will ripple throughout other layers. This theory relates to the core of this study because it studies a child's development then, it must look not only at the child and his immediate environment, but also at the interaction of the larger environment as well.

Objectives

This study sought to find out the teachers' attitude towards multiculturalism and diversity of learners in relation to Grade 10 student's academic performance in Araling Panlipunan in the Division of Bacolod City as basis for teachers development program. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the teachers' attitude towards multiculturalism when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 2) the teachers' attitude towards diversity of learners when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 3) the level of students' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan; 4) the significant difference in the teachers' attitude on multiculturalism when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; 5) the significant difference in the teachers' attitude towards diversity of learners when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; 6) the significant relationship between the teachers' attitude on multiculturalism and the students' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan; and 7) significant relationship between the teachers' attitude on diversity of learners and the students' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan.

Methodology:

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive research design in determining the teachers' attitude towards multiculturalism and diversity of learners in relation to students' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan 10 in the Division of Bacolod City during School Year 2016-2017 as basis for development program. It is the nature of this study to determine the conditions of things in their present state. It delves into the relationships and/or comparisons among variables that are considered in the study as well as the influence of one variable to another. Based on this premise, the researcher considered it most appropriate to use the descriptive research design. According to Devin Kowalczyk (2015), descriptive design is used to describe characteristics of population or phenomenon being studied. It answers questions about how/when/why the characteristic occurred. It is a study to depict the participants in an accurate way. More simply, descriptive research is all about describing people who take part in the study, and it can be done using observational, case study or survey.

Study Respondents

The respondents of this study were the 22 public secondary schools and 36 Araling Panlipunan teachers in Grade ten of this research in the Division of Bacolod City. The purposive sampling was used. Purposive sampling is where a researcher selects a sample based on the needs about the study. The participants are selected based on the purpose of the sample. Participants are selected according to the needs of the study.

Instruments

This study utilized enhanced questionnaires based on the Munroe Multicultural Attitude Survey Questionnaire (MASQUE) and the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards-Teachers' Strengths and Needs Assessment (NCBTS-TSNA) to assess teachers' multicultural attitudes and their perception of learner diversity. The survey included 20 items for each category, with responses rated on a five-point scale. Teachers' attitudes toward multiculturalism were classified as Highly Positive, Moderately Positive, Uncertain, Moderately Negative, or Highly Negative. Similarly, learner diversity was rated on a scale from Very Great Extent to Very Low Extent, with corresponding score ranges for interpretation. Validation average is 4.58, interpreted as "excellent". This showed that the research instrument was "Valid". And the reliability result was 0.819 in the area of attitude towards multiculturalism, and .954 in the area of diversity of learners, both interpreted as "high reliability".

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission through written communication from the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division of Bacolod City. When granted with permission, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaires to each of the respondents in different secondary public schools. The purpose of the study is properly explained. Computations are processed with the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software. Likewise, statistical tables were constructed as per consideration of the objectives that are stated in this study.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objectives 1, 2, and 3 employed descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the teachers' attitude towards multiculturalism, extent of diversity of learners and student's academic performance when they grouped according to aforementioned variables.

Objectives 4, 5 and 6 utilized comparative analytical scheme and Mann Whitney U test to determine the significance existing between the teachers' attitude towards multiculturalism, extent of diversity of learners and level of students' academic performance when the respondents are grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables. Comparative analytical scheme is employed to weigh against at least two groups in certain variables.

Objective 7 utilized relational analytical scheme and Spearman Rho Coefficient of Correlation to determine whether or not there is a significant relationship exists between teachers' multicultural attitude, the extent of diversity of learners and students' academic performance.

Ethical Consideration

Participants' personal demographic information results were collected and were noted in the data capturing sheet. Informed consent via verbal communication was elicited with the respondents. They read and understood the provided information and can ask questions. Moreover, their participation was voluntary, and they were free to withdraw without giving any reasons. The respondents were assured that there would be no risks of harm will experience before, during, or after participating in the research. The data and information used in the study were treated with strict confidentiality. No statement regarding the participant's identity was disclosed unnecessarily in this study. After the data gathering, since there was no need, debriefing was not done by the researcher anymore, as cited in the Data Privacy Act.

Results and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1
Teachers' Attitude towards Multiculturalism According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Pride in one's culture	4.42	Highly Positive	4.58	Highly Positive
2. Ethnicity inside the classroom	4.08	Moderately Positive	4.25	Highly Positive
3. Social barriers	3.79	Moderately Positive	3.92	Moderately Positive
4. Different religious beliefs	4.33	Highly Positive	4.25	Highly Positive
5. Gender equality	4.58	Highly Positive	4.25	Highly Positive
6. Cultural differences among my Students	4.21	Moderately Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
7. Sexual preferences	3.88	Moderately Positive	4.17	Moderately Positive
8. Diverse cultural values	4.21	Moderately Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
9. Different student's skills	4.42	Highly Positive	4.08	Moderately Positive
10. Student's sexual orientation	4.17	Moderately Positive	3.83	Moderately Positive
11. Respecting religious differences	4.46	Highly Positive	4.33	Highly Positive
12. Student's financial status	4.29	Highly Positive	3.92	Moderately Positive
13. Student's status in life	4.17	Moderately Positive	3.83	Moderately Positive
14. Student's income status	4.08	Moderately Positive	3.92	Moderately Positive
15. Student's language use	4.17	Moderately Positive	3.92	Moderately Positive
16. Students with disabilities	4.08	Moderately Positive	3.75	Moderately Positive
17. Communication gap	3.67	Moderately Positive	3.58	Moderately Positive
18. Students preferred sexual orientation	3.62	Moderately Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
19. Favoritism inside my class	2.50	Moderately Negative	2.83	Uncertain
20. Embarrass or ridicule students in the classroom	2.46	Moderately Negative	2.58	Moderately Negative
Overall Mean	3.75	Moderately Positive	3.67	Moderately Positive

The Teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism according to sex is rated "moderately positive" by both male and female respondents with mean scores of 3.60 and 3.76, respectively. The male respondents rated most of the items as "moderately positive", except for Items 1 and 5 which were given a "highly positive" rating and Items 3, 17, 19,

and 20 which were interpreted as "uncertain." Equally, the female respondents rated most of the items "moderately positive" except for Items 1,4,5,6,9,and 11 which were rated as "highly positive" and Items 19 and 20 which were rated as "moderately negative." Teachers' attitude towards multiculturalism according to sex, both male and female respondents had shown the same interpretation as "moderately positive". This implies that female teachers are more aware in gender equality of students compare to male teachers. The result showed that female teachers are more concerned in dealing with the "embarrassment/ridicule students inside the classroom" compared to male teachers. The study of Escobin (2014), revealed that teachers' work attitude did not significantly differ when they were grouped according to sex, length of service and educational attainment.

Table 2
Teachers' Attitude towards Multiculturalism According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Pride in one's culture	4.38	Highly Positive	4.50	Highly Positive
2. Ethnicity inside the classroom	3.88	Moderately Positive	4.21	Moderately Positive
3. Social barriers	3.88	Uncertain	3.96	Moderately Positive
4. Different religious beliefs	4.21	Moderately Positive	4.36	Highly Positive
5. Gender equality	4.25	Highly Positive	4.54	Highly Positive
6. Cultural differences among my students	3.75	Moderately Positive	4.25	Highly Positive
7. Sexual preferences	3.62	Moderately Positive	4.07	Moderately Positive
8. Diverse cultural values	4.12	Moderately Positive	4.14	Moderately Positive
9. Different student's skills	4.12	Moderately Positive	4.36	Highly Positive
10. Student's sexual orientation	3.62	Moderately Positive	4.18	Moderately Positive
11. Respecting religious differences	4.12	Moderately Positive	4.50	Highly Positive
12. Student's financial status	4.12	Moderately Positive	4.18	Moderately Positive
13. Student's status in life	3.45	Moderately Positive	4.14	Moderately Positive
14. Student's income status	3.88	Moderately Positive	4.07	Moderately Positive
15. Student's language use	4.00	Moderately Positive	4.11	Moderately Positive
16. Students with disabilities	3.62	Moderately Positive	4.07	Moderately Positive
17. Communication gap	3.25	Uncertain	3.75	Moderately Positive
18. Students preferred sexual orientation	3.50	Moderately Positive	3.82	Moderately Positive
19. Favoritism inside my class	2.88	Uncertain	2.45	Moderately Negative
20. Embarrass or ridicule students in the classroom	2.88	Uncertain	2.39	Moderately Negative
Overall Mean	3.60	Moderately Positive	3.75	Moderately Positive

The Teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism according to civil status is rated "moderately positive" by both single and married respondents with mean scores of 3.74 and 3.71, respectively. The single respondents rated most of the items as "moderately positive", except for Items 1,2,4,5,8,9,11, and 12 which were given a "highly positive" rating, and Items 19 and 20 which were interpreted as "moderately negative." Likewise, the married respondents rated most of the items "moderately positive" but with the exception of Items 1, 5, and 11 which were rated as "highly positive" and Items 19 and 20 which were rated as "uncertain." The result shows that single teachers are more receptive compared to the married counterparts. Research suggests that, generally, married teachers tend to have a positive attitude towards multiculturalism, often showing a greater openness to embracing diversity in the classroom compared to unmarried teachers, though the difference may not always be statistically significant; however, individual attitudes can vary greatly based on personal experiences and beliefs, regardless of marital status. Moreover, while specific studies focusing exclusively on married teachers' attitudes toward multiculturalism are limited, research has explored teachers' attitudes toward multicultural education more broadly. For instance, Akcaoglu (2021) examined the impact of a multicultural education course on teachers' attitudes and found significant positive effects on their perspectives toward cultural differences and a reduction in prejudices. Additionally, a study by Ponterotto et al. (1998) investigated teachers' multicultural attitudes and their relationship to culturally responsive teaching practices, highlighting the importance of positive attitudes in effectively implementing multicultural education. These studies suggest that targeted multicultural education can positively influence teachers' attitudes, though they do not specifically address marital status as a variable.

Table 3
Teachers' Attitude towards Multiculturalism According to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Pride in one's culture	4.50	Highly Positive	4.45	Highly Positive
2. Ethnicity inside the classroom	4.43	Highly Positive	3.95	Moderately Positive

3. Social barriers	4.07	Moderately Negative	3.68	Moderately Positive
4. Different religious beliefs	4.43	Highly Positive	4.23	Moderately Positive
5. Gender equality	4.50	Highly Positive	4.45	Highly Positive
6. Cultural differences among my students	4.14	Moderately Positive	4.14	Moderately Positive
7. Sexual preferences	4.14	Moderately Positive	3.86	Moderately Positive
8. Diverse cultural values	4.50	Highly Positive	3.91	Moderately Positive
9. Different student's skills	4.43	Moderately Positive	4.23	Moderately Positive
10. Student's sexual orientation	4.21	Moderately Positive	3.95	Moderately Positive
11. Respecting religious differences	4.50	Highly Positive	4.36	Highly Positive
12. Student's financial status	4.29	Highly Positive	4.09	Moderately Positive
13. Student's status in life	4.07	Moderately Positive	4.05	Moderately Positive
14. Student's income status	4.14	Moderately Positive	3.95	Moderately Positive
15. Student's language use	4.14	Moderately Positive	4.05	Moderately Positive
16. Students with disabilities	4.00	Moderately Positive	3.95	Moderately Positive
17. Communication gap	3.57	Moderately Positive	3.68	Moderately Positive
18. Students preferred sexual orientation	4.00	Moderately Positive	3.59	Moderately Positive
19. Favoritism inside my class	2.43	Moderately Negative	2.73	Uncertain
20. Embarrass or ridicule students in the classroom	2.29	Moderately Negative	2.64	Uncertain
Overall Mean	3.75	Moderately Positive	3.71	Moderately Positive

The Teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism according to highest educational attainment is rated "moderately positive" by both the respondents with Lower and Higher educational attainment, with mean Scores of 3.72 and 3.75, respectively. The respondents with Lower educational attainment rated most of the items as "moderately positive", except for Items 1, 4, 5, and 9 which were given a "highly positive" rating and Items 19 and 20 which were interpreted as "moderately negative." Though the study of Escobin (2014), revealed that teachers' work attitude did not significantly differ when they were grouped according to sex, and length of service. The Teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism according to the length of service is rated "moderately positive" by both respondents having shorter and longer length of service with mean scores of 3.60 and 3.89, respectively. The respondents with shorter length of service rated most of the items as "moderately positive", except for Items 1, 5, 8, and 9 which were given a "highly positive" rating and Items 19 and 20 which were interpreted as "moderately negative". Similarly, respondents with longer length of service rated most of the items "moderately positive" except for Items 1, 4, and 5 which were rated as "highly positive" and Items 19 and 20 which were rated as "uncertain." The result showed that teachers with longer length of service are more concerned with the pride in one's culture, different religious beliefs, and gender equality. Moreover, respondents with shorter length of service are more aware of the existing gender equality of students and different student skills. However, the study of Escobin (2014), showed that teachers' work attitude did not significantly differ when they were grouped according to sex, length of service and educational attainment.

Table 4
Teachers' Attitude towards Multiculturalism According to Length of Services

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Pride in one's culture	4.43	Highly Positive	4.53	Highly Positive
2. Ethnicity inside the classroom	4.10	Moderately Positive	4.20	Moderately Positive
3. Social barriers	3.76	Moderately Positive	3.93	Moderately Positive
4. Different religious beliefs	4.19	Moderately Positive	4.47	Highly Positive
5. Gender equality	4.52	Highly Positive	4.40	Highly Positive
6. Cultural differences among my students	4.19	Moderately Positive	4.07	Moderately Positive
7. Sexual preferences	3.95	Moderately Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
8. Diverse cultural values	4.29	Highly Positive	3.93	Moderately Positive
9. Different student's skills	4.52	Highly Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
10. Student's sexual orientation	4.19	Moderately Positive	3.87	Moderately Positive
11. Respecting religious differences	4.33	Moderately Positive	4.53	Moderately Positive
12. Student's financial status	4.14	Moderately Positive	4.20	Moderately Positive
13. Student's status in life	3.95	Moderately Positive	4.20	Moderately Positive
14. Student's income status	4.00	Moderately Positive	4.07	Moderately Positive
15. Student's language use	4.19	Moderately Positive	3.93	Moderately Positive
16. Students with disabilities	3.86	Moderately Positive	4.13	Moderately Positive
17. Communication gap	3.43	Moderately Positive	3.93	Moderately Positive
18. Students preferred sexual orientation	3.62	Moderately Positive	3.93	Moderately Positive
19. Favoritism inside my class	2.24	Moderately Negative	3.13	Uncertain
20. Embarrass or ridicule students in the classroom	2.29	Moderately Negative	2.80	Uncertain

Overall Mean	3.60	Moderately Positive	3.89	Moderately Positive
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The Teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism according to religion is rated "moderately positive" by both Catholic and non-Catholic respondents with mean scores of 3.71 and 3.75, respectively. The Catholic respondents rated most of the items as "moderately positive", except for Items 1,2,4,5,8,9,10, and 11 which were given a "highly positive" rating, and Items 19 and 20 which were interpreted as "moderately negative". Moreover, the older respondents rated most of the items "moderately positive" except for Items 1 and 5 which were rated as "highly positive" and Items 17,19, and 20 which were rated as "uncertain". Catholic teachers gave importance on gender equality and respect religious differences. Non-Catholic teachers are proud of our one's culture. It simply shown that non-Catholic teachers displayed an honor and pride in one's culture which is a good example for the students.

Table 5
Teachers' Attitude towards Multiculturalism According to Religion

Items	Catholic		Non-Catholic	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Pride in one's culture	4.42	Highly Positive	4.58	Highly Positive
2. Ethnicity inside the classroom	4.29	Highly Positive	3.83	Moderately Positive
3. Social barriers	3.96	Moderately Positive	3.58	Moderately Positive
4. Different religious beliefs	4.46	Highly Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
5. Gender equality	4.54	Highly Positive	4.33	Highly Positive
6. Cultural differences among students	4.17	Moderately Positive	4.08	Moderately Positive
7. Sexual preferences	4.04	Moderately Positive	3.83	Moderately Positive
8. Diverse cultural values	4.25	Highly Positive	3.92	Moderately Positive
9. Different student's skills	4.38	Highly Positive	4.17	Moderately Positive
10. Student's sexual orientation	4.33	Highly Positive	3.50	Moderately Positive
11. Respecting religious differences	4.54	Highly Positive	4.17	Moderately Positive
12. Student's financial status	4.21	Moderately Positive	4.08	Moderately Positive
13. Student's status in life	4.00	Moderately Positive	4.17	Moderately Positive
14. Student's income status	4.04	Moderately Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
15. Student's language use	4.08	Moderately Positive	4.08	Moderately Positive
16. Students with disabilities	3.96	Moderately Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
17. Communication gap	3.75	Moderately Positive	3.42	Uncertain
18. Students preferred sexual orientation	3.71	Moderately Positive	3.83	Moderately Positive
19. Favoritism inside my class	2.38	Moderately Negative	3.08	Uncertain
20. Embarrass or ridicule students in the classroom	2.42	Moderately Negative	2.67	Uncertain
Overall Mean	3.71	Moderately Positive	3.75	Moderately Positive

The Teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism according to average monthly income is rated "moderately positive" by all respondents who have Lower and Higher average monthly income with mean scores of 3.75 and 3.67, respectively. The respondents with Lower monthly income rated most of the items as "moderately positive", except for Items 1,4,5,9, and 12 which were given a "highly positive" rating and Items 19 and 20 which were interpreted as "uncertain". Likewise, respondents with Higher monthly income rated most of the items "moderately positive" except for Items 1,2,4,5,9, and 11 which were rated as "highly positive" and Items 19 and 20 as "moderately negative". Teachers with higher average family income are prouder of being a Filipino compare with respondents with lower average family income. It implies that both lower and higher average family income respondents have highly positive attitude in our own culture regardless of their income.

Table 6
Teachers' Attitude towards Multiculturalism According to Average Monthly Family Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Pride in one's culture	4.39	Highly Positive	4.62	Highly Positive
2. Ethnicity inside the classroom	4.04	Moderately Positive	4.31	Highly Positive
3. Social barriers	3.87	Moderately Positive	3.77	Moderately Positive
4. Different religious beliefs	4.30	Highly Positive	4.31	Highly Positive
5. Gender equality	4.43	Highly Positive	4.54	Highly Positive
6. Cultural differences among students	4.09	Moderately Positive	4.23	Moderately Positive
7. Sexual preferences	3.87	Moderately Positive	4.15	Moderately Positive
8. Diverse cultural values	4.13	Moderately Positive	4.15	Moderately Positive

9. Different student's skills	4.30	Highly Positive	4.31	Highly Positive
10. Student's sexual orientation	4.00	Moderately Positive	4.15	Moderately Positive
11. Respecting religious differences	4.39	Highly Positive	4.46	Highly Positive
12. Student's financial status	4.26	Highly Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
13. Student's status in life	4.04	Moderately Positive	4.08	Moderately Positive
14. Student's income status	3.96	Moderately Positive	4.15	Moderately Positive
15. Student's language use	4.00	Moderately Positive	4.23	Moderately Positive
16. Students with disabilities	3.91	Moderately Positive	4.08	Moderately Positive
17. Communication gap	3.43	Moderately Positive	4.00	Moderately Positive
18. Students preferred sexual orientation	3.57	Moderately Positive	4.08	Moderately Positive
19. Favoritism inside my class	2.83	Uncertain	2.23	Moderately Negative
20. Embarrass or ridicule students in the classroom	2.65	Uncertain	2.23	Moderately Negative
Overall Mean	3.70	Moderately Positive	3.75	Moderately Positive

Table 7
Teachers' Attitude towards the Diversity of Learners According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	4.08	High	3.67	High
2. Identity learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.88	High	3.67	High
3. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.75	High	3.83	High
4. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	4.38	Very High	3.92	High
5. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	4.25	Very High	3.92	High
6. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.08	High	3.67	High
7. Pace lessons according to learners' needs and difficulties	4.04	High	3.58	High
8. Keep track of students-at-risk	3.92	High	3.50	High
9. Provide appropriate intervention programs for learners-at-risk	3.79	High	3.33	Moderate
10. Know the cultural background of students and its implications to teaching	3.88	High	3.50	High
11. Provide appropriate learning activities to students with different cultural background	3.88	High	3.67	High
12. Show sensitivity to learners	4.25	Very High	4.08	High
13. Understand the effects of socio economic status on the learning performance	4.17	High	4.08	High
14. Determine the different socio-economic backgrounds of learners	4.00	High	3.75	High
15. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	3.79	High	3.58	High
16. Identify learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.92	High	3.58	High
17. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.88	High	3.75	High
18. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	3.83	High	4.00	High
19. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	3.71	High	3.58	High
20. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.08	High	4.08	High
Overall Mean	3.98	High	3.74	High

The Teachers' understanding towards the diversity of Learners according to age is rated "high extent" by both Younger and Older respondents with mean scores of 3.98 and 3.74, respectively. The Younger respondents rated most of the items as "high", except for Items 4, 5, and 12 which were given a "very high" rating. Moreover, the older respondents rated all items as "HIGH." The result shown that younger teachers are more understanding compare to the older ones. In item 4, "Show respect and concern for individuals' differences of students which is interpreted as "very high". Item 5. "Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners" which is interpreted as "very high". And item 12, "Show sensitivity to learners". According to Jeremy Harmer (2015), there are four fundamental responsibilities of teachers such as creating the need, giving feedback, creating the right atmosphere and passing on knowledge. Being supportive and helping the students to overcome their weaknesses is crucial to students' progress. One of chief responsibilities of a conscientious teacher is to create the right kind of respectful and supportive learning environment. This involves setting the right kind of challenges, effective group leadership and ensuring that all are treated equally.

Table 8

Teachers' Attitude towards the Diversity of Learners According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	3.75	High	4.00	High
2. Identity learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.62	High	3.86	High
3. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.88	High	3.75	High
4. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	4.12	High	4.25	Very High
5. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	4.12	High	4.14	High
6. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	3.88	High	3.96	High
7. Pace lessons according to learners' needs and difficulties	3.62	High	3.96	High
8. Keep track of students-at-risk	3.62	High	3.82	High
9. Provide appropriate intervention programs for learners-at-risk	3.25	Moderate	3.75	High
10. Know the cultural background of students and its implications to teaching	3.25	Moderate	3.89	High
11. Provide appropriate learning activities to students with different cultural background	3.75	High	3.82	High
12. Show sensitivity to learners	3.88	High	4.29	Very High
13. Understand the effects of socio economic status on the learning performance	4.12	High	4.14	High
14. Determine the different socio-economic backgrounds of learners	4.25	Very High	3.82	High
15. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	3.88	High	3.68	High
16. Identify learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.62	High	3.86	High
17. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.62	High	3.89	High
18. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	4.00	High	3.86	High
19. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	3.62	High	3.68	High
20. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.12	High	4.07	High
Over all mean	3.80	High	3.92	High

The Teachers' understanding towards the diversity of Learners according to sex is rated "high extent" by both male and female respondents with mean scores of 3.80 and 3.92, respectively. The male respondents rated most of the items as HIGH, except for Items 9 and 10 which were rated "moderate" and Item 14 which was given a "very high" rating. Likewise, the Female respondents rated most of the items as HIGH except for Items 4 and 12 which were rated as "very high". Item 4, "Show respect and concern for individual differences of students", which is interpreted as "very high". Item 12, "Show sensitivity to learners" which is also interpreted as "very high". It implies that female respondents are more sensitive and concern with the individual differences than the male respondents. Gardner introduced the theory of multiple intelligences in a popular book in the early 1980s. The theory posited seven different intelligences: logical-mathematical, linguistic, spatial, musical, bodily - kinesthetic, interpersonal, and intrapersonal. Gardner's theory to issues about individual differences is cognitive functioning. With respect to the traditional approaches to intellectual abilities, Gardner makes several key claims as follows: a) intelligence is plural, not singular; b) individuals differ in their profiles of intelligences or abilities; c) intellectual assessment should not be limited to paper-pencil tests but should include "more humane methods"; d) intelligence should not be expanded to include personality, motivation, will, attention, character, and other important and significant human capabilities (Gardner, 1999).

Table 9

Teachers' Attitude towards the Diversity of Learners According to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	4.14	High	3.82	High
2. Identity learning styles and multiple intelligences	4.00	High	3.68	High
3. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.79	High	3.77	High
4. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	4.57	Very High	4.00	High
5. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	4.50	Very High	3.91	High
6. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.07	High	3.86	High

7. Pace lessons according to learners' needs and difficulties	4.07	High	3.77	High
8. Keep track of students-at-risk	3.79	High	3.77	High
9. Provide appropriate intervention programs for learners-at-risk	3.57	High	3.68	High
10. Know the cultural background of students and its implications to teaching	3.79	High	3.73	High
11. Provide appropriate learning activities to students with different cultural background	4.00	High	3.68	High
12. Show sensitivity to learners	4.43	Very High	4.05	High
13. Understand the effects of socio economic status on the learning performance	4.36	Very High	4.00	High
14. Determine the different socio-economic backgrounds of learners	4.29	Very High	3.68	High
15. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	4.07	High	3.50	High
16. Identify learning styles and multiple intelligences	4.21	High	3.55	High
17. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	4.21	High	3.59	High
18. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	4.14	High	3.73	High
19. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	3.79	High	3.59	High
20. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.29	Very High	3.95	High
Overall Mean	4.10	High	3.77	High

Both single and married teachers rated their attitude toward learner diversity as "high extent," with mean scores of 4.10 and 3.77, respectively. Single respondents showed a slightly higher level of understanding, rating several items as "very high," particularly in respecting individual differences, considering learners' experiences and capabilities, showing sensitivity, and understanding socio-economic backgrounds. Geneva Gay (2010) emphasized that culture shapes culturally responsive teaching, encompassing values, beliefs, and traditions that influence education. Teachers play a vital role in acknowledging and addressing these differences, ensuring that all students receive structured and inclusive instruction, ultimately contributing to their academic progress.

Table 10

Teachers' Attitude towards the Diversity of Learners According Length of Service

Items	Shorter Mean Interpretation		Longer Mean Interpretation	
1. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	4.05	High	3.80	High
2. Identity learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.90	High	3.67	High
3. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.76	High	3.80	High
4. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	4.29	Very High	4.13	High
5. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	4.14	High	4.13	High
6. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	3.86	High	4.07	High
7. Pace lessons according to learners' needs and difficulties	3.86	High	3.93	High
8. Keep track of students-at-risk	3.76	High	3.80	High
9. Provide appropriate intervention programs for learners-at-risk	3.62	High	3.67	High
10. Know the cultural background of students and its implications to teaching	3.71	High	3.80	High
11. Provide appropriate learning activities to students with different cultural background	3.81	High	3.80	High
12. Show sensitivity to learners	4.10	High	4.33	Very High
13. Understand the effects of socio economic status on the learning performance	4.10	High	4.20	High
14. Determine the different socio-economic backgrounds of learners	4.00	High	3.80	High
15. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	3.81	High	3.60	High
16. Identify learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.81	High	3.80	High
17. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.86	High	3.80	High
18. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	3.95	High	3.80	High
19. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	3.71	High	3.60	High
20. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.10	High	4.07	High
Overall Mean	3.91	High	3.88	High

The Teachers' attitude towards the diversity of Learners according to length of service is rated "high extent" by both respondents having shorter and longer length of service with mean scores of 3.91 and 3.88, respectively. The respondents with shorter length of service rated most of the items as "high", except for Item 4 which was rated "very high". Likewise, the Female respondents rated most of the items HIGH except for Item 12 which was rated as "very high". Teachers' attitude towards diversity according to highest educational attainment, the result shown that teachers with lower educational attainment have more respect and concern for individual differences of students. According to "Effective Teacher Traits", care for students was the most common personal trait of effective teachers while for students was pointed as a necessity for effective teachers to gain credibility with students.

Table 11
Teachers' Attitude towards the Diversity of Learners According Religion

Items	Catholic		Non-Catholic	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	4.12	High	3.58	High
2. Identity learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.83	High	3.75	High
3. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.75	High	3.83	High
4. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	4.38	Very High	3.92	High
5. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	4.29	Very High	3.83	High
6. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.00	High	3.83	High
7. Pace lessons according to learners' needs and difficulties	3.96	High	3.75	High
8. Keep track of students-at-risk	3.83	High	3.67	High
9. Provide appropriate intervention programs for learners-at-risk	3.62	High	3.67	High
10. Know the cultural background of students and its implications to teaching	3.75	High	3.75	High
11. Provide appropriate learning activities to students with different cultural background	3.79	High	3.83	High
12. Show sensitivity to learners	4.29	Very High	4.00	High
13. Understand the effects of socio economic status on the learning performance	4.17	High	4.08	High
14. Determine the different socio-economic backgrounds of learners	4.00	High	3.75	High
15. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	3.92	High	3.33	Moderate
16. Identify learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.96	High	3.50	High
17. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.92	High	3.67	High
18. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	3.92	High	3.83	High
19. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	3.75	High	3.50	High
20. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.17	High	3.92	High
Overall Mean	3.97	High	3.75	High

Both Catholic and non-Catholic teachers rated their attitude toward learner diversity as "high extent," with mean scores of 3.97 and 3.75, respectively. Catholic respondents showed greater sensitivity to individual differences, rating respect for diversity and student needs as "very high," while non-Catholic respondents rated their understanding of multiple intelligences as "moderate." Overall, recognizing learners' diverse capabilities enhances curriculum delivery and supports student needs. According to "Religious Diversity and Intercultural Education," fostering respect for different beliefs and values is essential in democratic societies to cultivate reflective and engaged citizens.

Table 12
Teachers' Attitude towards the Diversity of Learners According Average Monthly Family Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	4.00	High	3.85	High
2. Identity learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.83	High	3.77	High
3. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.70	High	3.92	High
4. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	4.35	Very High	4.00	High

5. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	4.22	High	4.00	High
6. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.04	High	3.77	High
7. Pace lessons according to learners' needs and difficulties	3.87	High	3.92	High
8. Keep track of students-at-risk	3.83	High	3.69	High
9. Provide appropriate intervention programs for learners-at-risk	3.70	High	3.54	High
10. Know the cultural background of students and its implications to teaching	3.74	High	3.77	High
11. Provide appropriate learning activities to students with different cultural background	3.87	High	3.69	High
12. Show sensitivity to learners	4.22	High	4.15	High
13. Understand the effects of socio economic status on the learning performance	4.17	High	4.08	High
14. Determine the different socio-economic backgrounds of learners	3.96	High	3.85	High
15. Understand the theories and concepts of multiple intelligences	3.70	High	3.77	High
16. Identify learning styles and multiple intelligences	3.83	High	3.77	High
17. Know techniques and strategies in designing or selecting activities for various types of learners	3.87	High	3.77	High
18. Show respect and concern for individual differences of students	3.87	High	3.92	High
19. Appropriate need to consider the differences in experiences and capabilities of learners	3.65	High	3.69	High
20. Know teaching principles and strategies for addressing learners' needs and difficulties	4.04	High	4.15	High
Overall Mean	3.92	High	3.85	High

The Teachers' attitudes towards the diversity of Learners according to average monthly income is rated "high extent" by both respondents with Lower and Higher average monthly income with mean scores of 3.92 and 3.85, respectively. The respondents with Lower income rated most of the items as "high", except for Item 4 which was given a "very high" rating on "Show respect and concern for individual differences of students." It implies that both respondents with lower and higher average monthly income are aware of the diversity of learners inside the classroom regardless of their income received. Moreover, the respondents with Higher average monthly income rated all items as "high".

Table 13

Level of Students' Academic Performance in Araling Panlipunan 10 According to Variables

Variable	Category	Mean	Interpretation
Age	Younger	81.10	Satisfactory
	Older	81.17	Satisfactory
Sex	Male	81.94	Satisfactory
	Female	80.89	Satisfactory
Civil Status	Single	81.94	Satisfactory
	Married	80.89	Satisfactory
Length of Service as Teachers	Shorter	80.83	Satisfactory
	Longer	81.52	Satisfactory
Religion	Catholic	81.15	Satisfactory
	Non-Catholic	81.07	Satisfactory
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	81.28	Satisfactory
	Higher	80.84	Satisfactory

Table 13 reveals that students' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan 10 is consistently rated as "satisfactory" across various demographic variables. Older respondents, males, singles, teachers with longer service, Catholics, and those with lower family income obtained slightly higher mean scores compared to their counterparts. However, the differences in mean scores were minimal, indicating that these factors had no significant impact on students' overall performance, which remained within the satisfactory range.

Table 14

Difference in Teachers' Attitude Towards Multiculturalism when grouped and compared according to Variables

Variable	Category	Mean	Mann U	Whitney -d value	Sig Level1	Interpretation
Age	Younger	3.75	127.5	.579	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	3.67				

Sex	Male	3.60	78.0	.194	Not Significant
	Female	3.76			
Civil Status	Single	3.74	151.5	.935	Not Significant
	Married	3.71			
Length of Service as Teachers	Shorter	3.60	98.0	.055	Not Significant
	Longer	3.89			
Religion	Catholic	3.71	143.0	.973	Not Significant
	non-Catholic	3.75			
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	3.70	148.0	.960	Not Significant
	Higher	3.72			

Table 14 shows that the difference in teachers' attitudes towards multiculturalism across various demographic variables, including age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, years of teaching experience, religion, and average family income, is not statistically significant. The Mann-Whitney test results indicate that all obtained p-values exceed the 0.05 significance level, suggesting that these factors do not significantly influence teachers' attitudes toward multiculturalism.

Table 15

Difference in Teachers' Attitude Towards Diversity of Learners when grouped and compared according to Variables

Variable	Category	Mean	Mann Whitney U	-d value	Sig Level1	Interpretation
Age	Younger	3.98	110.0	.253		Not Significant
	Older	3.74				
Sex	Male	3.80	101.5	.689		Not Significant
	Female	3.92				
Civil Status	Single	4.10	88.5	.033		Not Significant
	Married	3.77				
Length of Service as Teachers	Shorter	3.91	146.0	.712	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	3.88				
Religion	Catholic	3.97	100.0	.139		Not Significant
	Non-Catholic	3.75				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	3.92	141.0	.779		Not Significant
	Higher	3.85				

According to civil status, the comparison of teachers' attitude towards the diversity of learners obtained a p-value of 0.033 which is interpreted as "not significant" at 0.05 level of significance. The significance in the difference between mean scores that describe the difference between the teachers' attitude towards the diversity of learners according to variables is shown in the table below. The data was treated using the Mann Whitney test for significance. The obtained p-value, when comparing the teachers' attitude towards the diversity of learners according to age, is 0.253 which is interpreted as "not significant" at 0.05 level of significance. When compared according to sex, the teachers' attitude towards diversity of learners obtained a p-value of 0.689 which is interpreted as "not significant" at 0.05 level of significance. The teachers' attitude, when compared according to number of years as Araling Panlipunan teachers, obtained a p-value of 0.712 which is interpreted as "not significant" at 0.05 level of significance. When compared according to religion, the teachers' attitude obtained a p-value of 0.139 which is interpreted as "not significant" at 0.05 level of significance. Comparing the teachers' attitude according to average family income, the obtained p-value is 0.779 which is interpreted as "not significant" at 0.05 level of significance. Over-all, the difference between the teachers' attitude towards diversity of learners when compared according to selected variables is "not significant."

Table 16

Difference in Teachers' Attitude towards Multiculturalism and Diversity of Learners

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation
Multiculturalism	.384	0.021	Significant
Diversity of Learners			

Table 16 below shows the significance in the relationship between mean scores that describe the teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism and towards the Diversity of Learners. The data was treated using the Spearman Rho test for significance. The obtained p-value, when comparing the teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism and towards the Diversity of Learners, is 0.021. It is interpreted as "significant" at 0.05 level of significance. This result showed that there is a significant difference in the teachers' attitude towards multiculturalism and diversity of learners.

Table 17

Relationship between the Teachers' Attitude towards Multiculturalism and the Students' Academic Performance

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation
Multiculturalism	.146	0.397	Not Significant
Academic Performance			

The significance in the relationship between mean scores that describe the teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism and Academic Performance is shown in Table 20. The data was treated using the Spearman Rho test for significance. The obtained p-value, when comparing the teachers' attitude towards Multiculturalism and towards the Diversity of Learners, is 0.397. It is interpreted as "not significant" at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 18

Relationship between the Teachers' Attitude toward Diversity of Learners and the Students' Academic Performance

Variables	Rho	p-value	Interpretation
Diversity of Learners	.453	0.006	Significant
Academic Performance			

The significance in the relationship between mean scores that describe the teachers' attitude towards the Diversity of Learners and Academic Performance is shown in Table 21. The data was treated using the Spearman Rho test for significance. The obtained p-value, when comparing the teachers' attitude towards Diversity of Learners and Academic Performance, is 0.006. The interpretation is "significant" at 0.05 level of significance. It is very crucial to the teachers to be mindful on how the students learn best in order for them to satisfy the needs of their diverse students (Gregory and Chapman, 2013). Teaching students the process individual differences and with the variety of learning styles really a big responsibility of the teachers that need to develop and enhanced. Educators should consider the academic differences of the learners to help them integrate the content of the curriculum to their own lives and modify the complexity of instruction so all students' experience learning success thus, making learning meaningful and intersecting to them (Green and Suban, 2006).

Conclusions:

The study found that respondents, predominantly younger female teachers with average income and mostly Roman Catholic, exhibited a "moderately positive" attitude toward multiculturalism, likely influenced by the Philippines' diverse cultural landscape and early exposure to multicultural concepts in education. However, their attitude toward learner diversity was rated as a "high extent," indicating strong recognition of students' varied needs, abilities, and challenges, which plays a crucial role in curriculum development. While teachers' attitudes toward multiculturalism did not significantly impact student academic performance, their approach to learner diversity showed a strong correlation, highlighting the need for tailored teaching strategies, particularly in Araling Panlipunan 10. The study recommends that the Department of Education facilitate teacher training programs on multiculturalism, adolescent psychology, and inclusive teaching methods through seminars and workshops. School heads should also support professional development by inviting experts, promoting higher education, and ensuring continuous monitoring and feedback. Teachers must embrace technological advancements and innovative teaching techniques to address the needs of diverse learners effectively. Future research should explore additional factors affecting teachers' attitudes and student performance, utilizing varied methodologies to enhance understanding and relevance.

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